

Politecnico
di Torino

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

CoARA Action Plan

Opinion of the Academic Senate on January 21, 2025,
and approval by the Board of Directors on January 30, 2025.

1. Premise

Since 2022, the European Commission has promoted an initiative within the European Research Area aimed at reviewing and updating current research assessment processes (of organizations and units, projects, and research personnel). The goal is to better recognize the diversity of research missions, disciplines, and outputs, as well as the methodologies and practices that maximize the quality and impact of research, also considering the changes in the research lifecycle brought about by digitalization. On September 20, 2022, the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) was presented to the University Quality Assurance Board (PQA) of Politecnico di Torino and subsequently, on September 27, to the Academic Senate. The document aims to outline a shared vision regarding the weaknesses of the current research assessment system and the necessary directions for its innovation. On October 6, 2022, Politecnico di Torino formally endorsed the ARRA by signing the agreement.

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) was established in December 2022, bringing together organizations that have signed the agreement—including research funding bodies, research-performing organizations, evaluation authorities and agencies, as well as associations of these organizations, scientific societies, and other relevant entities. The coalition's objective is to collaborate—while respecting the autonomy of individual institutions—to reform current research assessment processes in line with the principles of the Agreement within an agreed timeframe.

The Agreement identifies general principles as the foundation for reform:

- Ensuring ethics and integrity, avoiding compromises due to conflicting incentives.
- Safeguarding scientific research freedom by creating flexible, non-restrictive assessment frameworks to be adopted as needed.
- Respecting the autonomy of research organizations, while avoiding contradictions between different levels of assessment and various institutions.
- Ensuring the independence and transparency of the data, infrastructures, and criteria used in research assessment.

Regarding evaluation criteria and processes, the Agreement outlines guiding principles in two dimensions: i) **quality and impact**, and ii) **diversity, inclusion, and collaboration**. These principles translate into **four fundamental, goal-oriented commitments**:

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon inappropriate use in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.

These core commitments are accompanied by six **operational supporting commitments**: three commitments that facilitate the transition to new criteria, tools, and processes for research assessment, and three others that promote mutual knowledge exchange, communication of progress made, and ensure that new assessment approaches are evidence-informed. Specifically:

5. Commit resources to research assessment reform to implement the necessary organizational changes.

6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools, and processes:

6.1. CRITERIA FOR UNITS AND INSTITUTIONS

With the direct involvement of research organisations and researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria for assessing research units and research performing organisations, while promoting interoperability.

6.2. CRITERIA FOR PROJECTS AND RESEARCHERS

With the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application.

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

2. Introduction

By signing the ARRA in June 2022 and actively participating in the Coalition, Politecnico di Torino aims to promote a culture of responsible and inclusive research assessment and the potential revision of the university's internal evaluation processes.

Regarding the general principles of CoARA, Politecnico di Torino recognizes, within its Statute¹, the principles of the European Charter for Researchers², fully endorses open access to scientific literature, and promotes the free dissemination of research results produced at the Institution.

In the past five years, Politecnico di Torino has established:

- A Regulation for Research Integrity and an Ethics Committee³;
- An Open Access Policy for publications⁴;
- A Research Data Management Policy aligned with open science principles⁵;
- A Gender Equality Plan (GEP) as part of the 2018–2024 strategic plan⁶.

In relation to CoARA's fundamental commitments, the institution prioritizes the following goals in its approach to research assessment and reform: a) Recognizing the diversity of research contributions and career paths. b) Focusing the assessment of individual researchers primarily on quality, using peer review, quantitative indicators responsibly, and any new tools as appropriate. Evaluation tools differ depending on whether the assessment targets individuals or structures; however, the institution is committed to ensuring a cohesive, comprehensive approach consistent with the goals and missions defined in its medium-term strategy.

In promoting reform actions within the institution, certain challenges must be addressed: the constraints imposed by the Italian research assessment system, the complexity arising from the diversity of research activities conducted by the internal academic community, and the limited awareness and dissemination of open science best practices.

To work through such challenges, Politecnico di Torino, as an actor capable of directing reforms and innovations in the university and research system, is committed to strengthening training initiatives, encouraging positive behaviors, fostering close collaboration with research organizations, MUR (Italian Ministry of Universities and Research), and ANVUR (National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes) within CoARA's framework, and actively involving researchers in defining appropriate goals and criteria to promote gradual and positive cultural change.

¹ https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2022-10/STATUTO_Politecnico_Torino_per%20pubblicazione_0.pdf

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2005/251/oj>

³ <https://www.polito.it/ricerca/principi-e-policy/integrita-ed-etica-nella-ricerca/comitato-etico>

⁴ <https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2022-10/Policy%20OA%20emanata%20DR%2087-2019.pdf>

⁵ <https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2024-02/PolicyDatiRicerca%202024.pdf>

⁶ https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2022-10/GEP%20it_PoliTO_Sito_new.pdf

Politecnico di Torino has established an internal working group (GdL), comprising representatives from teaching and research staff and PTAB (technical-administrative staff), responsible for supporting and monitoring the reform project in accordance with CoARA's principles.

The GdL has overseen the process of joining CoARA and conducted a state-of-the-art analysis prior to drafting the Action Plan. The identified actions will be incorporated into the Institution's Strategic Plan for 2024–2030, ensuring alignment with the Institution's objectives.

PoliTO GdL Members:

- Federica Cappelluti: Director of the Center for Open Science Studies;
- Gianluca Setti: Expert in research assessment and Rector's Representative for the evaluation of research quality;
- Arianna Montorsi: Director of the Gender Studies Center;
- Antonina Maria Marino: Area Manager (STARQ – Strategy, Analysis, Reporting, and Quality)
- Luigi Erriquens: Head of Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Services Division (STARQ – Strategy, Analysis, Reporting, and Quality);
- Mauro Paschetta: Domain expert in Open Science (ARIA – Library System Service);
- Alessandra Cerato: Area Official, Library Sector (STARQ – Quality, Assessment, and Enhancement of Research and Knowledge Services Division).

2. Current Status

2.1 Transparent Communication, Training, and Exchange of Best Practices

Politecnico di Torino promotes a policy that encourages the mutual exchange of best practices and decision-making transparency at the institutional level, actively involving the academic community through outreach, mentoring, and tutoring activities, as well as targeted training for PhD students and early-career researchers.

The University has already implemented measures to ensure transparent communication regarding internal evaluation processes for structures, with all information accessible on a dedicated institutional webpage⁷. Regulations are accessible to both internal and external members of the University. Evaluation methods, both for institutional structures and individuals, are communicated in a targeted manner: in particular, "welcome" seminars for newly appointed faculty and research staff address assessment topics, presenting the university's guidelines and the offices that provide support.

Specific training activities related to evaluation focus on the use of thematic dashboards as support for assessment⁸ and on Open Science.

2.2 Open Science

Politecnico di Torino identifies the principles and tools of Open Science as an opportunity for growth for the University's research, with significant impact for education and its broader cultural mission. The institution also aims to acknowledge and reward contributions, activities, and pathways related to research at all stages.

Specifically:

- Since 2019, calls for positions as First and Second-tier Professors evaluate the impact of the overall scientific output "using indicators outlined for national scientific qualifications for each tier and disciplinary area, along with the presence of open science products associated with publications." However, the open science dimension is not included in calls for early-career researchers, and there is certainly room to increase evaluators' awareness of open science practices and outputs.
- Support and training are provided by specialized staff.
- Seminars and outreach events⁹ on Open Science are offered.
- The training program for PhD students includes a course on Open Science and research data management, as well as a course on research integrity.

⁷ <https://www.polito.it/en/polito/quality/quality-of-research>

⁸ <https://www.polito.it/en/polito/quality/strategy-implementation-and-monitoring>

⁹ <https://www.polito.it/impatto-sociale/biblioteche-di-ateneo/open-access/convegni-seminari-e-progetti-di-ateneo>

2.4 Evaluation in Recruitment and Career Progression

Politecnico has embraced the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, receiving the HR Excellence in Research Award¹⁰ in 2013 through the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)¹¹ initiative. In parallel, the institution has launched major initiatives to strengthen the evaluation of applications in calls for **recruitment and career advancement for Full and Associated Professors**, adopting a more holistic and inclusive approach. This approach, partially already in place, aims to assess not only scientific activity but also research group/project coordination, Third Mission activities, national and international reputation, teaching activities and institutional services and assignments at Italian and foreign universities and/or public or private entities with scientific and/or technology transfer goals.

In calls for Full and Associated Professors, the structure of the assessment involves three sub-areas for evaluating the candidates' scientific activities:

- a) The three main results/products of research activity.
- b) A set of publications submitted by the candidate (with a maximum limit typically set at 20).
- c) The overall scientific output.

The evaluation committee has the discretion to assign different weights to each sub-area, with the requirement that sub-area (a) has the predominant weight, aiming to prioritize quality-based assessment. Sub-areas (b) and (c) present potential issues related to CoARA's guiding principles, as committees could place too much emphasis on quantitative parameters such as the number of products and citations, h-index, journal quality indicators, and indicators aligned with national scientific qualifications.

Calls for **early-career researchers** include evaluation of scientific output and qualifications. The assessment of scientific output mainly involves an analytical evaluation of submitted publications (typically with a maximum limit of 12), complemented by an evaluation of the overall scientific output. Regarding evaluations for **seniority salary increases**, a streamlined process is implemented, proportionate to the individual and institutional impact of the evaluation, aiming to verify that the candidate meets threshold results in teaching, scientific publishing, and managerial responsibilities. Therefore, no additional actions are included in the Action Plan. Concerning **diversity and inclusion** in recruitment and evaluation processes, calls for faculty and research positions include a statement encouraging applications from women and minorities. Additionally, during candidate selection, the committee declares that it has reviewed the purposefully provided video on *unconscious bias*.

¹⁰ <https://www.polito.it/en/polito/work-with-us/working-in-research/hr-excellence-in-research/human-resources-strategy-for-researchers-hrs4r>

¹¹ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r>

2.5 Internal Evaluation of Research Structures

Politecnico di Torino's active participation in the National Chapter (NC)¹² and CoARA's Working Groups (WGs)¹³ reflects its commitment to a conscious and responsible internal evaluation of its research structures.

Organizationally, the University is structured into eleven departments that coordinate and promote research activities, as well as manage teaching. Resources are allocated to departments based on an evaluation that considers scientific output, funding (both from competitive grants and technology transfer activities), and teaching.

Research output is assessed through both results from the National Agency for the Evaluation of Research (ANVUR) and an internal evaluation based on the University's bibliometric criteria. For this purpose, the University applies differentiated evaluation criteria depending on the disciplinary group (GSD). For those in bibliometric GSDs, the evaluated outputs include journal articles, book chapters, peer-reviewed conference proceedings, and patents, with consideration of four journal impact indicators. For non-bibliometric GSDs, the same product types are evaluated, with the addition of books and edited volumes. This evaluation considers journal impact indicators where available, as well as national evaluation parameters for books and chapters, including qualitative indicators such as the publishing house and quantitative measures like internationalization levels. Comprehensive guidance is also provided for the use of bibliometric indicators.

The University has an integrated dashboard system supporting strategic planning¹⁴ definition, implementation, and monitoring. Specifically, the publication dashboard¹⁵ is a simple, continuously updated monitoring tool designed to give faculty and research staff visibility into their national standing through bibliometric indicators available on the platform, which can easily be combined. This tool allows analysis of trends in research output through national benchmarking, fostering a culture of self-assessment and the responsible use of bibliometric indicators.

2.6 Rankings

The University monitors the major international rankings but does not use them for resource allocation or awarding incentives. No actions are planned.

¹² <https://www.coara-italia.it/>

¹³ <https://coara.eu/coalition/working-groups/>

¹⁴ <https://www.polito.it/en/polito/quality/strategy-implementation-and-monitoring>

¹⁵ https://www.polito.it/sites/default/files/2024-02/Cruscotto_pubblicazioni_22_dicembre_2022_def_organized.pdf

3. Action Plan

The tables detailing the planned actions are provided in a separate document (**Annex 1 – ACTIONS**), which accompanies this analysis and offers a more comprehensive overview of the initiatives in relation to the CoARA strategy and commitments.

**Politecnico
di Torino**

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

www.polito.it